

Transition Metal Chelates of Salicylaldehyde and *p*-Phenylenc-Diamine

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Copper and cobalt chelates of salicylaldehyde and *p*-phenylenediamine have been prepared. Visible absorption spectra, magnetic susceptibility and thermal analysis of these chelates have been studied and discussed.

IN continuation of our studies on the transition metal chelates of salicylaldehyde and diamines¹, we present here our studies on copper and cobalt chelates of salicylaldehyde and *p*-phenylenediamine.

Experimental

(i) *Cu (II) and Co (II) chelates of salicylaldehyde*: Metal acetate dissolved in 50% alcohol was mixed with salicylaldehyde in the same solvent (salt : ligand :: 1 : 2). The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 3 hr. The precipitate was stirred, filtered, washed with water, alcohol and ether and dried.

(ii) *Reaction of metal chelates with p-phenylenediamine*: The chelate of Cu(II) or Co(II) with salicylaldehyde dissolved in alcohol was mixed with alcoholic solution of *p*-phenylenediamine (metal chelate : diamine :: 1 : 2) and refluxed on water-bath for 3-4 hr and left overnight. The product was filtered, washed with water, alcohol and ether and dried. The compounds are insoluble in water and common organic solvents except dimethylformamide and dioxane in which they are sparingly soluble. Their m.pt., colour, etc. are presented in table I.

Visible spectra: Absorption spectra (see Fig. 1) in the visible range (400 to 800 nm) were obtained for

these compounds in dimethylformamide using a Spekol spectrophotometer.

Magnetic Susceptibility: Magnetic susceptibility (χ_g) of these chelates was determined on Gouy's magnetic balance at 32° using mercury (II) tetrathiocyanato cobaltate (II) as the reference compound. The results are presented in table I.

No.	Chelate	Colour	M.P. °C	Mass magnetic susceptibility $\times 10^6$
1.	SAP—Cu	dirty green	> 300	3.56
2.	SAP—Co	dirty red	> 300	18.26

Thermal analysis: Thermal analysis (T.G.A.) of the chelates was carried out in nitrogen atmosphere at a heating rate of 10°/min., using Lenseis model. The results are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Visible absorption spectra of SAP-Cu and SAP-Co

— * — * — SAPCu
— ● — ● — SAPCo

Fig. 2. TGA Curves (SAP-Cu and SAP-Co)

— * — * — SAPCu
— ● — ● — SAPCo

Discussion

SAP-Cu: It was prepared from bis(salicylaldehyde) copper (II) and *p*-phenylenediamine. (Found: %Cu = 14.54; %N = 9.07; $C_{23}H_{18}N_3O_2Cu$ requires %Cu = 14.72 %N = 9.73). On the basis of elemental analysis, its empirical composition is $(CuLaqp_2)_n$, where LH_2 represents the Schiff base of salicylaldehyde and *p*-phenylenediamine, *p* is *p*-phenylenediamine and aq. is water.

The absorption band in the visible region is observed at 440 nm. Its magnetic moment per Cu-atom is calculated as 2.05 B.M. The stepwise weight losses observed in T.G.A. studies indicate that the chelate loses water and *p*-phenylenediamine and the loss is accompanied by the decomposition of the complex.

On the basis of the above observations copper in the chelate is considered to be 5-coordinated^{2,3}. It is believed that *p*-phenylenediamine cross-links the adjacent molecule.

SAP-Co: It was prepared from bis(salicylaldehyde) cobalt (II) and *p*-phenylenediamine. (Found: %Co = 9.85; %N = 12.27; $C_{29}H_{30}N_5O_4Co$ requires %Co = 10.31; %N = 12.26). On the basis of analysis, its empirical composition is $(CoLaq_2p_{3/2})_n$. It is known that bis(N-R-salicylaldimine) cobalt (II) (R = phenyl, N-butyl) becomes solvated in pyridine and acquires octahedral configuration. (Dipyridinated adducts were isolated and their spectra were studied)^{4,5}. Its magnetic moment per cobalt atom is calculated as 5.14 B.M. Hence the monomer is considered to have an octahedral structure.

It has an absorption band in the visible region at 490 nm. The ligand field band may be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transition.

The stepwise weight losses observed in T.G.A. studies indicate that at low temperature water is readily removed, on further heating it loses *p*-phenylenediamine and at higher temperature it decomposes probably leaving the residue of cobalt.

On the basis of the above observations the complex is considered to have an octahedral configuration with cross-links formed with adjacent molecules through *p*-phenylenediamine.

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